

THE AFRICA–EUROPEAN UNION STRATEGIC PARTNERSHIP

Investing in People, Prosperity and Peace

Council of the
European Union

THE AFRICA–EUROPEAN UNION STRATEGIC PARTNERSHIP

Investing in People, Prosperity and Peace

Council of the
European Union

Notice

This publication is produced by the General Secretariat of the Council and is intended for information purposes only. It does not involve the responsibility of the EU institutions nor the member states.

For further information on the European Council and the Council, you can consult the following websites:

www.european-council.europa.eu

www.consilium.europa.eu

or contact the Public Information Service of the General Secretariat of the Council:

Rue de la Loi/Wetstraat 175

1048 Bruxelles/Brussel

BELGIQUE/BELGIË

Tel. +32 (0)2 281 56 50

Fax +32 (0)2 281 49 77

public.info@consilium.europa.eu

www.consilium.europa.eu/infopublic

More information on the European Union is available on the Internet (www.europa.eu).

Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2014

ISBN 978-92-824-4656-0

doi:10.2860/55618

© European Union, 2014

Reuse is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Printed in Belgium

PRINTED ON ECOLOGICAL PAPER

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Foreword by Herman Van Rompuy, President of the European Council	5
Foreword by José Manuel Barroso, President of the European Commission	6
Foreword by Mohamed Ould Abdel Aziz, Chair of the African Union, President of Mauritania	8
Foreword by Nkosazana Dlamini-Zuma, Chairperson of the African Union Commission.	9
Summit declaration	11
Roadmap 2014–2017	25
Thematic declaration on migration	44
List of participants.	47
List of EU–Africa summits.	64

FOREWORD BY HERMAN VAN ROMPUY, PRESIDENT OF THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL

The 4th EU-Africa Summit brought together in Brussels more than 60 EU and African leaders, and a total of 90 delegations, including the Secretary General of the United Nations, to discuss the future of EU-Africa relations and reinforce links between the two continents. With this impressive attendance, the Summit underlined the importance that both Africa and Europe attribute to this relationship.

Our societies, our continents change rapidly – and it is essential that we meet regularly to take stock of where we are, and where we want to go. What is a constant, however, is our commitment to maintaining a privileged partnership between our two continents.

The traditional approach of Europe as aid distributor and of Africa as passive beneficiary has long ceased to correspond to reality. There is a deep consensus on both sides about the need for a strategic partnership of equals.

The 4th EU-Africa Summit was a decisive step towards this goal. Under the headline theme 'Investing in People, Prosperity and Peace', we identified the best ways to strengthen the bonds between us. The themes chosen address people's everyday concerns - their safety, their security, their job prospects, and their future as families and individuals. We agreed that together we now must deliver tangible results in these areas over the next three years.

Our two continents, intimately connected by history and culture, look towards a shared future. Our cooperation has brought undeniable progress in recent years, but there is still much to be done. I am delighted that our two continents are continuing this journey together.

FOREWORD BY JOSÉ MANUEL BARROSO, PRESIDENT OF THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

The EU and Africa are neighbours and thus natural partners. We are connected by a common sea and despite living on two different continents our peoples share a single vision, namely that of a more prosperous, stable and open Europe and Africa. We also share the will to work hand in hand to make this vision come true.

In an increasingly interdependent and fast-changing world, Europe's and Africa's future are closely interlinked. From the threats to peace, democracy and economic prosperity to the fight against poverty and climate change, what affects Africa affects Europe and vice-versa.

This is why we have embraced together a new forward-looking vision: the Joint Africa–EU Strategy adopted at the Lisbon Summit in 2007 which established a partnership of equals and goes beyond development to tackle issues of common interest.

Fulfilling the vision set out in our Joint Strategy, the 4th EU–Africa Summit held in early April in Brussels not only reaffirmed the strong solidarity and mutual respect that guide our cooperation, but also seized further cooperation opportunities by 'investing in people, prosperity and peace'. And whilst the fundamentals of our Joint Strategy were re-confirmed, we also agreed to adapt it to evolving challenges.

By bringing together 54 African and 28 European countries, as well as the African and European Union institutions, the Brussels Summit resulted in the adoption of an ambitious Declaration, which calls for an even stronger political dialogue between both partners.

We also agreed on a new Roadmap that will allow us to make the most of our partnership. In the years ahead we will be able to go from strength to strength by working together to resolve peace and security crises to enforce human rights and improve good governance, to step up collaborative research and to facilitate student mobility, to promote continental integration through trade and infrastructure, as well as to ensure sustainable agriculture and food and nutrition security.

And we are fully committed to work together to address key development challenges such as migration. It is a complex challenge that we are ready to approach in a constructive manner as shown by the adoption of a joint declaration on our cooperation in this crucial area. We must all do more to prevent tragedies like the ones off the coast of Lampedusa.

Strengthening people-to-people contacts and human networks between our continents will also bring benefits for both sides. From the business communities to researchers and academics; from civil society organisations to the European and African youth all are eager and ready to engage.

In this spirit the widely praised Business Forum held just before the Summit delivered pertinent messages to the Heads of State and Government and highlights that a strong emphasis on private sector and African development as well as the promotion of an investment and business-friendly environment are key to ensuring sustainable and inclusive economic growth.

Moreover, the organisation of an Africa–EU Civil Society Forum in October 2013, a Youth Summit in March 2014 and the discussion on human rights during a Parliamentary Summit between the European and the Pan-African Parliament bear testimony to the people-centred dimension of the Africa–EU Partnership.

This is indeed what our partnership is fundamentally about: to make a real difference in our citizens' day-to-day lives. This is a unique partnership, based on shared values that are at the core of the African Union and of the European Union, enshrined in the African Charter on Democracy, Elections and Governance as well as in the EU's Treaty of Lisbon. This is a partnership which is more relevant than ever and I am confident that together we will make sure that it can live up to its full potential and deliver tangible results to our citizens.

FOREWORD BY MOHAMED OULD ABDEL AZIZ, CHAIR OF THE AFRICAN UNION, PRESIDENT OF MAURITANIA

More than 50 years ago, the generation of our founding fathers laid the groundwork for what has become a vital institutional framework lending expression to African unity and solidarity.

That coming together within the framework of the Organisation of African Unity, now the African Union, draws its impetus not only from a shared history, with all its moments of glory and of suffering, but also from the promises of a shared ideal.

That we have been able to preserve our eminent unitary organisation through a half-century marked by fratricidal conflicts, which have been as painful as they have been senseless, is due precisely to the steadfast attachment of the African peoples to their unity.

The ideal of unity, constantly reaffirmed by all Member States of the African Union, pushes us to strengthen our links with our neighbours and our partners. The EU–Africa summit held in Brussels on 2 and 3 April 2014 under the theme ‘Investing in People, Prosperity and Peace’ is a shining manifestation of this.

We are convinced that we must close the chapter of conflict and inequitable relations, and look with hope to a future of shared interests founded on the immense opportunities offered by the establishment of a new type of relationship between Africa and Europe.

In this relationship, whose precise objectives equate to an obligation to achieve results, it is of paramount importance to establish a solid partnership based on trust and mutual interest. It is against the backdrop of this optimistic outlook for the shared future of our two continents that the joint declaration adopted by the Heads of State and Government at the Brussels summit should be viewed.

I wish to take this opportunity to pay tribute to the determination and commitment that characterised that encounter; its successful outcome will mark a turning point in relations between the African Union and its European partner. It will surely transform the face of the Afro-European partnership in the near future and pave the way for a fruitful win-win relationship in which the future looks bright.

FOREWORD BY NKOSAZANA DLAMINI-ZUMA, CHAIRPERSON OF THE AFRICAN UNION COMMISSION

African and European leaders have spoken. We have demonstrated that there is much that we can and must do together to confront common challenges and take advantage of opportunities and to secure peace and security and achieve rapid, resilient and inclusive as well as sustainable social and economic development for our people.

We have come together not simply as neighbours or because of our shared history. We have come together because we face common challenges and a shared future as peoples of one planet earth that invites all global citizens to pay attention to sustainability considerations.

We are all agreed that our people must be at the centre of our joint endeavour and especially women and youth.

There is a great deal of convergence of how to confront challenges to peace and security and sustainable development as well as the need for strong institutional mechanism, to address root causes and a rapid response mechanism. We in Africa greatly appreciate the support from Europe through the Peace Support Fund. Africa remains determined to silence all guns by 2020.

We have committed ourselves on the need for transformation of Africa's economy through investment in industry, agriculture and infrastructure and through access to finance, markets and transfer of technology.

In order to take advantage of the demographic dividends, Africa seeks support to impart skills to the youthful population and access to means of production and markets. In addressing the phenomenon of human migration we must face up to the push and pull factors. To boost intra-Africa trade, create regional value chains, and encourage private investments we are committed to developing a Continental Free Trade Area by building on achievements of the Regional Economic Communities.

Lest we are misunderstood. Africa is very much alive to the reality that the new trade regime under the WTO calls for reciprocity, which takes into account developmental needs of Africa. We therefore call the EU as partners to ensure that Economic Partnership Agreements do not frustrate Africa's integration and development agenda.

Partnerships are always stronger when founded on mutual trust, goodwill and respect. We trust that our long-standing partnership will remain guided by these values.

EUTM Somalia – Graduation of Somali soldiers in Mogadishu

EUFOR RCA, Bangui, Central African Republic

DECLARATION

INTRODUCTION

1. We, Heads of State and Government of the European Union (EU) and Africa, the President of the European Council, the President of the European Commission, the President of the African Union (AU) and the Chairperson of the African Union Commission (AUC), met in Brussels on 2–3 April 2014. We took as our theme ‘Investing in People, Prosperity and Peace’, with the objective of addressing common challenges and bringing concrete benefits to our citizens in accordance with the Joint Africa–EU Strategy (JAES). Recognising the high degree of interdependence between Africa and Europe and guided by the shared principles of equal partnership and joint ownership, we take particular pride in the breadth and depth of our partnership, which is firmly rooted in our shared values of democracy, the respect for human rights, rule of law and good governance as well as the right to development.
2. We reaffirm our commitment to the objectives set out in the Joint Africa–EU Strategy adopted at our Summit in Lisbon in 2007. We take note of the very real progress made, including in the Tripoli Declaration of our third Summit in 2010, and reaffirm our determination to give a new momentum to our partnership. We agree to mobilise resources to this end.
3. Since 2010, important developments have taken place on our continents.
4. Africa has achieved significant progress in democracy, governance and human rights which however remains to be consolidated. Africa has experienced pronounced economic growth: a growing number of countries and people are reaching middle income status and attracting increased investment flows. Yet this growth has not been sufficiently inclusive or even, both between as well as within countries. The Continent continues to face significant challenges. Africa is celebrating the 50th Anniversary of the Organisation of African Unity/African Union. There is an opportunity for a transformation at continental, regional and national levels to ensure that Africa’s potential is realised and its economic integration achieved in a sustainable manner and in line with the AUC Strategic Plan 2014–2017 and Africa’s Transformation 2063 Agenda. This will enable Africa to become a key player in the global arena.
5. The EU economy suffered a recession but returned to a path of growth in 2013. Job creation will remain a serious challenge and an important priority, especially in providing employment opportunities for young people. The EU has made significant progress in strengthening the architecture of its

Economic and Monetary Union, deepening its Single Market, implementing the Treaty of Lisbon and undertaking structural reforms by Member States to pave the way for smart, sustainable, and inclusive growth as well as for regulating their financial sector.

6. We are convinced that the growth of our two continents will be mutually beneficial: our economies remain closely linked, and we will work to ensure that the growth of the one will help the other. We are also convinced that trade and investment and closer economic integration on each of our continents will accelerate that growth.
7. People must remain at the heart of our partnership, so we pledge today to provide them with the opportunities they need. It is the essence of our partnership that we tackle these challenges more effectively if we tackle them together, to the benefit of our citizens. Our joint agenda will have people, prosperity and peace and security at its core.

PEACE AND SECURITY

8. Peace and Security are essential prerequisites for development and prosperity. In Africa and in Europe, conflict and instability can undermine all our efforts to reduce poverty and to accelerate growth. We pledge to ensure a transparent, democratic, accountable and peaceful environment for those we represent, and to uphold our common values and goals in pursuit of good governance, democracy and the rule of law. We commit ourselves to respect all rights and principles set out in the Treaties and Charters that we have respectively signed and ratified, and to work together in all countries to respect our peoples' demands for justice, reconciliation, respect for international law, human rights, gender equality and dignity.
9. We reaffirm our commitment to peace and security on both our continents in conformity with the aims and principles of the United Nations Charter.
10. We confirm our rejection of, and reiterate our commitment to fight, impunity at the national and international level. We undertake to enhance political dialogue on international criminal justice, including the issue of universal jurisdiction, in the agreed fora between the two parties.
11. We strongly support the African aspiration and commitment to ensure peace, security and stability in Africa, in the framework of the African Peace and Security Architecture (APSA). In order to improve the African capacity to predict and prevent or respond to crises, we are committed to operationalise the multidimensional African Standby Force and to recognise the African Capacity for Immediate Responses to Crises (ACIRC), as a transitional and complementary tool to the African Standby Force for further enhancing the

AU's capacity to respond rapidly to crises, and to reinforce the support to the Continental Early Warning System. We welcome the progress made to date in enhancing the capacity of the AU and regional organisations to manage crises on the continent. We acknowledge the successful deployment of peace support operations by the AU in Darfur (Sudan), Somalia, Mali and the Central African Republic, and the collective efforts in the Great Lakes and South Sudan to reduce conflict in those countries. We pay tribute to those who have lost their lives fighting to preserve peace or who suffered as victims of those conflicts.

12. We agree to support these efforts to enhance African capacities in the field of peace and security through the range of means at our disposal, with a particular focus on capacity-building. This should enable African partners such as the AU, regional organisations and individual countries to better provide for security and stability in their own regions. The African Peace Facility has played a crucial role in supporting AU operations and the APSA, so we agreed to sustain the level of resources available to it and to seek ways of redefining targets, while complementing it with African resources. Within the framework of the EU's comprehensive approach to tackling conflicts and its causes, and building on experiences of Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP) missions and operations, such as those in Mali, Niger, Democratic Republic of Congo, Somalia and the Central African Republic, the EU remains committed to work in close collaboration with Africa, in the framework of the APSA, in support of African led peace operations and, more generally, African efforts in areas like Security Sector Reform, Border Management, Peacebuilding or Post-Conflict Reconstruction or Reconciliation, through the provision of advice, mentoring and training. In addition, the supply of equipment is an option, either as a complement to CSDP missions and operations or as part of stand-alone measures.
13. We undertake to strengthen our common efforts to fight international terrorism, its related threats and transnational organised crime, including the trafficking of human beings, wildlife, natural resources, and drug smuggling.
14. We remain committed to combat the spread of small arms and light weapons as well as the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction.
15. We continue to work together to fight illegal fishing and illegal dumping of toxic waste.
16. We undertake to cooperate more closely in preventing conflicts and further agree on the importance of tackling the root causes of instability, fragility and conflict in order to prevent its recurrence and achieve sustainable recovery in line with the International Dialogue on Peacebuilding and Statebuilding,

as well as AU initiatives in this area. We support post-conflict reconstruction, so that after each conflict, efforts are undertaken for populations to benefit from peace dividends.

17. We underline the importance of addressing all aspects of the conflict cycle from preventive action through to post conflict reconstruction and development. We agree that justice and nationally inclusive reconciliation processes are crucial for sustainable peace and pledge to support efforts of African partners and regional organisations in this respect.
18. We reaffirm our willingness to protect women and children affected by armed conflicts, prevent sexual violence particularly affecting women and children, and promote gender mainstreaming in the prevention, management and resolution of conflicts and crises and in all stages of the peace-building process, in line with the UN Security Council resolution 1325.
19. We recognise the particular importance of tackling growing threats to maritime safety and security, including piracy. We acknowledge the international efforts off the coast of the Horn of Africa in which the EU naval operation Atalanta has been playing a key part. In this regard, we agree that emphasis should also be placed on addressing poverty and underdevelopment as possible causes of piracy. In order to achieve concrete results we undertake to work together to support the building of local maritime and judicial capacities to deal with these threats, in line with Africa's

EU NAVFOR Atalanta, Horn of Africa, Somalia

Integrated Maritime Strategy 2050 and with the EU Integrated Maritime Policy, through CSDP mission EUCAP Nestor and by enhancing regional cooperation in both the Horn of Africa and in the Gulf of Guinea. Africa and the EU recognise and encourage initiatives taken by African countries bordering the Atlantic with a view to promoting peace and security in that area.

20. In responding to these threats to peace and security on our two continents, we recognise the vital importance of the international community acting together. We therefore reaffirm our determination to ensure that multilateral institutions and treaty regimes are the main fora for international cooperation on peace and security. Essential for success is close cooperation between ourselves, with the relevant regional and sub-regional organisations, the UN and its agencies, and with other international coordination mechanisms such as the G8++ clearing house for Africa.
21. We are committed to addressing non-traditional challenges to peace and security in areas such as climate change, water, energy and cybersecurity which have an increasing influence on economic and social development.
22. Moreover, we recognize the need for further reform of the main UN bodies to make the whole UN system more efficient and transparent and adapt it to substantial changes that have occurred in the international community and for members of the UN.

PROSPERITY

23. We pledge ourselves to pursue policies, together with social partners, that will create jobs and stimulate environmentally sound, inclusive, sustainable and long-term growth on both continents.
24. In Africa, such policies shall promote economic transformation based on agriculture, green growth, industrialisation and value addition, the development of economic infrastructure and the service sector. We stress the importance of good governance at the highest level and of a conducive international environment including the international economic and financial institutions as elements contributing to the achievement of sustained and inclusive development and economic growth.
25. We will cooperate more closely in the field of maritime policy, especially blue growth, protection of the marine environment and biodiversity, maritime transport and maritime safety and security.
26. The EU and Africa are determined to adopt, in Paris in 2015, a fair, equitable and legally binding Agreement under the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change and guided by its principles, which will apply to all parties

Agriculture in Burkina Faso. Water is usually scarce and hence needs to be used consciously

and come into effect by 2020 at the latest. This Agreement should have a more universal and more efficient scope to produce results in terms of mitigation, adaptation, finance, technology development and transfer, transparency of action and support and capacity building. The EU and Africa are committed to initiate or intensify domestic preparations for their intended nationally determined contributions towards achieving the ultimate objective of the Convention and to communicate them well in advance of the twenty-first session of the Conference of the Parties by the first quarter of 2015, by those parties ready to do so. The EU is determined to support Africa in this regard.

27. The EU recognises that developed country parties should maintain continuity of mobilisation of public finance at increasing levels from the fast-start finance period in line with their joint commitment of mobilising USD 100 billion per year by 2020 from a wide variety of sources in the context of adaptation and meaningful mitigation and transparency of implementation.
28. The EU will continue to support African countries in the preparation of national and regional climate-resilient and low-emission development strategies to reinforce the resilience of their economies to climate change, in particular in sectors such as agriculture and access to sustainable and renewable energy in the context of the United Nations Sustainable Energy for all Initiative.
29. We recognise the vulnerability and the specific challenges faced by Small Island Developing States (SIDS), some of which are in Africa. We take note of the upcoming Conference organised for their benefit by the UN in Samoa and we will work together to making it a success.
30. We recognise that investment in research, science, technology and innovation is fundamental to achieve those objectives in particular, and to sustainable development of our societies in general. With this in mind,

we welcome the High Level Policy Dialogue on science, technology and innovation held between the two continents.

31. We want to foster strong domestic growth and use our respective resources efficiently to our people's advantage in the global economy. The transformation of agriculture to provide food resilience, food and nutrition security and a dynamic commercial sector is particularly important in Africa. To this end, we therefore agree to support in the framework of NEPAD the Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme whose objective is notably to achieve higher growth by developing a better functioning agriculture market and to ensure region-wide food security. We take note of developments in the EU Common Agricultural Policy and we will work towards achieving progress as regards coherence with the objectives of agricultural development in Africa.
32. Proactive measures are required to address the problems of land degradation, desertification and drought affecting many regions in Africa. We take note of the signature of a cooperative arrangement between our two Commissions to use European space science and technology to monitor ecosystems through the 'Global Monitoring for Environment and Security (GMES) and Africa' initiative.
33. We recognise that preserving existing and creating new jobs including in the manufacturing sector is a high priority for both continents. Faster industrialisation and modernisation of the enterprise sector is essential for many African countries which is to be premised inter alia on the transformation and value-addition of raw materials at the source as a catalyst for industrial development which is essential to reach middle income status. We commit to ensure prudent and transparent management of respective natural resources in the interest of our populations in particular in conflict affected areas in line with principles of good governance. In order to complement the African policies in the above fields, the EU recalls its approach to responsible mineral sourcing and proposes a dialogue on these issues.
34. We will continue our cooperation to preserve biodiversity and ecosystems on both continents.
35. We pay particular attention to how to encourage greater investment within our countries, between our continents and from outside. There is a need to improve the business climate in order to make it favourable for attracting internal and foreign investors and for existing businesses, including small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) which have a particularly vital role in job creation. Access to affordable credit, stable political, judicial and regulatory environments, and labour markets respecting international labour standards

are important factors in all our countries. So too is promoting corporate social responsibility and building greater transparency in finance to help combat corruption and illicit financial flows, including through the development of fair and effective tax systems.

36. To allow for the economies of scale that can stimulate such investment and growth, we confirm our strong belief that greater economic integration is necessary. Important elements to this include building productive supply capacity to take advantage of more fair and open trade, building up the markets to facilitate it, and putting in place the necessary infrastructure and governance reform measures for investments to be successful. We look to the private sector, in partnership with government, to play a larger role in economic growth and development.
37. On the way to greater economic integration, we will cooperate to develop transport, access to drinking water and to sustainable and affordable energy, with a particular focus on renewable energy and energy efficiency. We recognise the strategic importance of promoting interconnections in the areas of energy and transport between the two continents.
38. We also recognise the important and strategic role of the 'virtual' infrastructures enabled by the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), in particular the internet. We agree to further boost the uptake of ICT and the roll-out of an inclusive, open and secure information society that contributes to growth, development and the full enjoyment of human rights. We recognise the importance of the protection and promotion of human rights online, in conformity with the Universal Declaration and relevant international treaties on Human Rights, including the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on economic, social and cultural rights.
39. We fully commit to the successful conclusion of the Doha Development Agenda and to the preparation of the World Trade Organisation's (WTO) post-Bali work programme which contributes to the greater integration of developing countries into the multilateral trading system. We will take all possible steps towards realising this commitment in line with the respective mandates on developing countries issues. The EU remains committed to support African countries engaged in the accession process to the WTO and we are committed to the implementation of the Trade Facilitation Agreement.
40. The EU pledges its support to the AU decision to fast track the establishment of a Continental Free Trade Area (CFTA) in Africa and offers to draw on its experience of building the Single Market to provide capacity support to this initiative. We will continue working on outstanding Economic Partnership

Agreements (EPAs) with the aim to foster intra-African trade, Africa's regional integration efforts and the planned CFTA. In this regard, both parties should continue negotiations on EPAs by exploiting all the possibilities to reach a satisfactory conclusion of development-oriented and WTO-compatible EPAs that promote African integration, economic transformation and industrialisation, and ensure the prosperity of nations to the benefit of both continents. It is important that Africa and Europe develop globally competitive industries that can succeed in today's global markets and contribute to sustainable development. EPAs should be structured to ensure that our trade expands and that it supports growth of intra-regional trade in Africa.

41. The EU and concerned North African countries are also committed to continue bilateral negotiations for Deep and Comprehensive Free-Trade Areas that will expand market access in areas not yet fully open.
42. We will explore modalities to exchange information on the implementation of trade agreements and their implications for Africa's regional integration and industrial development agenda.
43. It is time for a fundamental shift from aid to trade and investment as agents of growth, jobs and poverty reduction. There is nevertheless still a valuable role for development assistance; we acknowledge the EU decision to maintain the level of its development assistance including aid for trade. We pledge to work together to make aid more effective.
44. We fully acknowledge the positive contribution to our debates from the EU–Africa Business Forum that took place in the margins of our Summit. We therefore support such engagements between the private sectors of our two continents on a regular basis.

PEOPLE

45. Upholding human rights in Africa and Europe is our duty and we will work together to ensure that the African Human Rights Year in 2016 is a success. Aware of the fact that the AU's vision is the realisation of 'An Integrated, prosperous and peaceful Africa, driven by its own citizens and representing a dynamic force in the global arena' and also taking into consideration the national dynamics of each African country, we will increase cooperation in support for international human rights and international humanitarian law. We shall hold regular consultations on civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights. We shall pay particular attention to gender equality, the rights of the most vulnerable groups, including people with disabilities, the elderly and refugees, as well as to women, youth and children's rights.

46. In the framework of our cultural cooperation we pledge to continue efforts in fighting the illicit trade in cultural goods and to work towards protecting national archives.
47. We are jointly committed to pursue our efforts towards reaching the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) by next year (2015). We are convinced that the post-2015 development agenda provides a unique opportunity to realise our common vision of a peaceful, just and equitable world that is free of poverty and respects the environment. We will work in partnership, during the upcoming negotiations, to support the definition and implementation of an ambitious, inclusive and universal post-2015 development agenda that should reinforce the international community's commitment to poverty eradication and sustainable development. We underline the need for a coherent approach which embraces the three dimensions of sustainable development – social, economic and environmental – in a more balanced and integrated manner, based on peace and security, and democratic, responsive and accountable institutions. In the spirit of our partnership, we will continue to cooperate closely in this endeavour.
48. All should be able to enjoy the dignity of work. We emphasise that jobs with labour rights, social security coverage and decent income contribute to more stable growth, enhance social inclusion and reduce poverty. We aim to unlock the entrepreneurial potential of our people with a special emphasis on women and youth – and to foster innovation in their businesses, so they can develop themselves, their communities and the wider economy. We confirm that as previously stated the achievement of these objectives will be accomplished by investing in science, technology and innovation and we commit to support cooperation in these fields.
49. We commit ourselves to equip our citizens insofar as we can with the knowledge, skills and services they need to take advantage of the opportunities that growth provides and lift the neediest from poverty. To that end, we will pursue policies that will promote inclusive job creation with a focus on young people and women, including through vocational training and education.
50. Higher education has a particularly important role to play in enhancing citizenship and democratic values as well as providing a country with the skilled workers, managers and administrators that will foster sustainable development and encourage the trade and investment needed. We agreed to promote student exchange programmes between our two continents and within Africa.

51. Providing affordable, sustainable and quality health care accessible to all, including access to medicines, is a particular challenge. We agreed to address it by intensifying our existing bi- and multilateral cooperation to give adequate attention to the development of productive capacity with particular emphasis on youth empowerment, women empowerment and gender equality, the eradication of poverty, education for developing human capital and the provision of universal and equitable access to quality healthcare.

Harvesting products on the farms

52. Migration, mobility and employment are key issues for us all. The serious social and human impact of irregular migration should be effectively tackled in a comprehensive way, including by addressing its root causes and among other means by ensuring an effective and concerted return policy between countries of origin, transit and destination.
53. We are appalled by the loss of life caused by irregular migration and remain more than ever committed to further action to avoid such tragedies in future. We reiterate our unambiguous commitment to continue fighting trafficking in human beings, which is a new form of slavery.
54. We are committed to ensure that human rights of all migrants, including those of the diaspora and victims of trafficking, are fully respected. We recognise the positive contribution that well-managed migration and mobility make to countries of origin, destination and to the migrants themselves. We will work together to mobilise the potential of migrants for development and to reduce the cost of remittances, including through the consolidation of the African Institute for Remittances. We set out our approach in more detail in the attached statement.
55. We are committed to fight all forms of discrimination, racism and xenophobia, and all acts of intolerance on both continents.
56. We affirm our commitment to join our efforts on pursuing the objectives of Africa and EU policies on labour employment and social protection with particular focus on SMEs.
57. We take note of the Africa–EU civil society organisations’ forum meeting of October 2013 and of the youth forum of April 2014.

IMPLEMENTATION

58. We took note of the scope and progress of our Partnership.
59. We reaffirm our desire to hold regular political dialogues at ministerial level, notably in the margins of international events.
60. We endorsed the Roadmap that sets out strategic priorities and identifies the means to implement them in areas of mutual interest and have agreed that our priorities for the period 2014–2017 are:

- Peace and Security;
- Democracy, Good Governance and Human Rights;
- Human Development;
- Sustainable and inclusive development and growth and Continental Integration;
- Global and emerging issues.

61. We will jointly pursue the identification, where needed of the working mechanisms and structures required to implement the agreed actions and reach the expected results.

62. We take note that implementation of the priorities will draw on a wide range of financing instruments and policy initiatives. Over the period 2014–2020, more than € 28 billion will be provided by the EU to Africa which will come in addition to bilateral cooperation on the part of EU Member States.

CONCLUSION

63. We agreed to meet again at our Fifth Summit in Africa in 2017.

EU–Africa Summit 2014, press conference

© European Union

© European Union

EU–Africa Summit 2014, plenary session

ROADMAP 2014–2017

INTRODUCTION

1. The Heads of State and Government of the European Union (EU) and Africa, the President of the European Council, the President of the European Commission, the President of the African Union (AU) and the Chairperson of the African Union Commission (AUC), meeting in Brussels on 2–3 April 2014, on the theme of ‘Investing in People, Prosperity and Peace’, committed to enhance Africa–EU cooperation for the years to come. They confirmed that the Joint Africa–EU Strategy (JAES), adopted at the Lisbon summit in 2007, setting out the vision, values and principles to which we are committed, remains the strategic political reference for EU–Africa relations. The summit praised the work done and the progress made in the implementation of the two preceding action plans.
2. The 4th EU–Africa summit agreed that the implementation of the Joint Strategy should be further improved in the light of experience and developments in Africa and Europe as well as globally. Our cooperation should be guided by a results-oriented approach. The summit therefore adopted the present document to frame continent-to-continent cooperation for the period 2014–2017. This document sets out key priorities and areas for joint actions at inter-regional, continental or global level in areas where Africa and the EU have mutual interests. It provides the necessary orientations for their implementation. These actions will be the object, for those that require it, of more detailed implementation plans.
3. The summit decided on actions in priority areas where cooperation between the two continents is essential, has high potential in the framework of the Joint Strategy and where substantial added-value can be expected. These actions will complement other initiatives undertaken as part of the cooperation between the EU and Africa at country and regional levels.
4. It was agreed to pursue and deepen political dialogue and cooperation. Summits, ministerial meetings, College-to-College meetings between the two Commissions and Peace and Security Council-to-Political and Security Committee meetings will continue to take place within the framework agreed for the Africa–EU Partnership at the Cairo Summit. This EU–Africa dialogue will be complemented by regular high level contacts between European and African leaders on common challenges and crisis situations.
5. In addition, given that some of the technical expert structures have not always been efficient, Africa and the EU shall jointly identify, where needed, the working mechanisms and structures required to implement the agreed actions and reach the expected results. The implementation of

the actions included in this roadmap will be assessed in the framework of joint annual forums which will replace the current Joint Task Force and will gather together all the actors of the Partnership. It was agreed to increase synergies between the political dialogue and cooperation and to promote contributions from the private sector and civil society.

JOINT PRIORITIES

6. For the 2014–2017 period, the summit agreed that the implementation of the Joint Strategy shall focus on the following priority areas:
 1. Peace and Security
 2. Democracy, Good Governance and Human Rights
 3. Human development
 4. Sustainable and inclusive development and growth and continental integration
 5. Global and emerging issues
7. For each of these objectives, a number of actions have been identified at inter-regional, continental or global levels which are expected to have a real impact on the people of both continents. It is important to note that these actions come in addition to cooperation at country and regional levels.

Priority area 1: Peace and Security

8. Strategic objective: To ensure a peaceful, safe, secure environment, contributing to human security and reducing fragility, foster political stability and effective governance, and to enable sustainable and inclusive growth.

Key areas for cooperation

9. We will enhance our political dialogue to discuss international issues, reach common positions and implement common approaches on challenges to peace and security in Africa, including addressing the issue of peace, justice and reconciliation. Such cooperation will take place notably through enhanced coordination between the AU Peace and Security Council and the EU Political and Security Committee. We confirm our rejection of, and reiterate our commitment to, fight impunity at the national and international level. We undertake to enhance political dialogue on international criminal justice, including the issue of universal jurisdiction, in the agreed fora between the two parties.
10. We will jointly pursue the identification, where needed, of the working mechanisms and structures required to implement the agreed actions and reach the expected results.

11. We will strengthen the operationalisation of the African Peace and Security Architecture (APSA), in particular by supporting the African Standby Force and its capacity to be deployed, supported and managed in a sustainable way. We will support training and capacity building of African forces, including police and civilian components. In addition, we will support the African institutional capacity building, for instance in the area of crisis prevention, peace building and post-conflict reconstruction including by providing advice, training and equipment.
12. We will strengthen coordination between the EU and Africa as well as with regional organisations in particular the Regional Economic Communities (RECs), in the planning and conduct of conflict prevention and peace support activities in cooperation, as appropriate, with the United Nations (UN).
13. We will increase cooperation in addressing the root causes of conflict and cross-cutting issues of common concern such as terrorism and related threats and transnational organised crime including trafficking in human beings drugs, arms trafficking and illegal trade in wildlife.
14. We will also pay special attention to the issue of maritime security including counter-piracy efforts, the fight against Illegal, Unregulated and Unreported fishing within the framework of the African Integrated Maritime Strategy 2050 and the EU Integrated Maritime Policy, and against toxic waste dumping.
15. We will strengthen the human rights dimension of our cooperation on peace and security, as much in conflict prevention efforts, crisis management and post-conflict processes, as in our efforts to improve good governance and to support Security Sector Reform. We will focus on ending sexual violence and on protecting civilians, in particular women and children who are the most affected by armed conflicts. We will ensure the full and effective participation and representation of women in peace and security processes.
16. In addition to current EU support to African-led Peace Support Operations and to the APSA through the African Peace Facility, we will strengthen mobilisation of African and international resources in order to improve the predictability and financial sustainability of African peace and security activities, notably African-led Peace Support Operations and management capacities of RECs and the AU.

Priority area 2: Democracy, Good Governance and Human Rights

This includes economic, social and cultural rights and civil and political rights

17. Strategic Objective: To ensure a transparent, democratic and accountable environment in the respect of Human Rights and the Rule of Law, contributing to reducing fragility, fostering political stability and effective governance, and enabling sustainable and inclusive development and growth.

Ceremony at the National Assembly for the adoption of the new Constitution of Tunisia, January 2014

Key areas for cooperation

18. The promotion of democratic governance remains at the core of our partnership. We will enhance our cooperation on democratic governance issues on both continents such as the fight against corruption and money laundering, strengthening the role of public sector institutions, including accountability and transparency, the rule of law and the governance of natural resources, including measures to curb their illegal exploitation.
19. We will also support the monitoring of elections by the African Union in the countries concerned and will ensure coordination with the electoral observation missions of the EU.
20. We will defend human rights in Africa and Europe and we will work together to make the African Human Rights Year in 2016 a success. We are united in the fight against impunity at national and international level and in the protection of human rights on both continents. We shall hold regular consultations on civil, political rights, economic, social and cultural rights. We shall pay particular attention to gender equality, the rights of the most vulnerable groups, including people with disabilities, the elderly and refugees, as well as to women, youth and children rights. A key framework for such dialogue will be the EU–AU Human Rights Dialogue.
21. We shall enhance dialogue between human rights institutions from both continents, including National Human Rights Institutions.
22. We shall increase our coordination and cooperation at the UN Human Rights Council and other international fora. We will ensure the full and active participation of civil society in our dialogue and our cooperation.
23. We will support the full operationalisation of the African Governance Architecture and the work achieved by its various organs including their necessary coordination. We will increase support for the efforts of concerned African countries to promote the ratification and the implementation of relevant treaties, including the African Charter on Democracy, Elections and Governance.

Culture

24. We will exchange experiences on the return of illegally exported or acquired goods to their countries of origin and encourage setting up relevant mechanisms for sharing best practices in particular on addressing archives issues.
25. We will work together towards an inclusive approach to culture as enabler and facilitator for development.

26. We will aim at strengthening cooperation to fight against illicit trafficking of cultural goods and to protect cultural goods, including national archives. We shall cooperate with relevant international organisations (in particular UNESCO, Interpol, World Customs Organisation, International Council of Museums and UN Office on Drugs and Crime) to ensure the coherence of these actions.
27. We will promote enhancement of tangible and intangible cultural heritage, as well as the diversity of cultural expressions by promoting cultural diversity, intercultural dialogue and international cooperation in the cultural field, in line with the UNESCO 2005 Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions.
28. We will cooperate to put in place digital inventories and archiving methods and to protect national archives. We are engaged to strengthen the safeguarding of World Heritage sites.

Priority area 3: Human development

29. Strategic objective: Promote human capital development and knowledge and skills based societies and economies, amongst others by strengthening the links between education, training, science and innovation, and better manage mobility of people. Our cooperation in the framework of the JAES will complement our actions at national level to improve access to more and better jobs and social protection, as well as access for all to quality basic education, sanitation and health care, including Sexual and Reproductive Health.

Improving health care

Key areas for cooperation

Science, technology and innovation

30. Investments in science, technology and innovation (STI) are vital to promote growth and employment, improve competitiveness and identify and address pressing global societal challenges such as climate change, affordable renewable energy and energy efficiency, infectious diseases or food and nutrition security. EU–Africa cooperation on STI is cross-cutting in nature, contributing to the attainment of all other socio-economic development

objectives. We will work towards reinforcing cooperation between research communities and the creation of joint academic research programmes, with a special focus on innovation and the productive sector including research infrastructures.

31. In addition, we will develop a long-term, jointly funded and managed research and innovation partnership, in particular in the areas of food and nutrition security and sustainable agriculture. We will take an integrated approach recognising the important cross-cutting nature of innovation/entrepreneurship, research infrastructures and technical skills development in Africa and Europe.
32. To this end, the EU–Africa High Level Policy Dialogue (HLPD) on science, technology and innovation will be the key platform in the JAES for priority-setting and implementation design. A HLPD expert working group will be set up that will be tasked with developing a detailed roadmap defining the scope and outlining the different steps to be taken towards this new partnership. Financing will come from the European Research and Innovation Programme, Horizon 2020, and other contributions from EU and African stakeholders.

Promoting education

School girls studying together at the “Girls’ Friendly Space” of Gambool High school in Somalia

Higher Education

33. Higher education plays a crucial role for economic and social development in catalysing sustainable development by producing high quality human resources and in disseminating the results of scientific and technical research. In addition to specific, traditional capacity building actions, mobility in itself has a strong potential to improve the quality of higher education, by accelerating the use of transparency and recognition tools, and by helping institutions develop better services to send and receive foreign students and researchers.
34. The Erasmus+ programme and Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions will allow for top-quality mobility of African and European students, scholars, researchers and staff through a balanced mix of actions centred on individuals, institutions and higher education systems. The Nyerere mobility programme will provide scholarships to around 500 students to undertake postgraduate studies and will allow for the mobility of 70 academic and administrative staff within Africa by 2017. This will promote student retention whilst increasing the competitiveness and attractiveness of the institutions themselves.
35. We will support the development of centres of excellence in Africa, particularly through the Pan-African University. We will expand the African Higher Education Harmonisation and Tuning pilot initiative with the aim to enhance the relevance and quality of curriculum, to introduce outcome-based teaching and learning, to increase from 60 to 120 the number of participating universities across the African continent and to increase the number of disciplines and levels addressed. In addition, boosting the African Union Higher Education Harmonization and Quality Assurance initiatives will

promote quality practices in universities and will support the implementation of the continental framework for quality assurance and accreditation, an increase of aligned partnerships and the internationalisation of higher education. We will consult and exchange to foster education, vocational training and entrepreneurship among women and youth.

Mobility and migration and employment

36. The Brussels summit adopted a Joint Declaration on Migration and Mobility and agreed to implement an Action Plan for the period 2014–2017. In line with this declaration, we will foster synergies between migration and development, including by reducing the costs of remittances, enhancing the role and engagement of the diaspora and consolidating the African Institute for Remittances. We will better organise intra and inter-regional labour mobility and that of business persons. We will enhance our cooperation to address trafficking in human beings, notably by strengthening partnership and cooperation on prevention, protection and prosecution. We will also cooperate on irregular migration, addressing all its relevant aspects, including strengthened migration management, return and readmission as well as the promotion of alternatives to irregular migration. Finally, we will cooperate together in the field of international protection and asylum, and will work together towards promoting respect of the human rights of migrants.

37. Our cooperation will be underpinned by a Migration and Mobility Dialogue steered by a core group of European and African countries and organisations meeting on a regular basis.

Priority area 4: Sustainable and inclusive development and growth and continental integration

38. Strategic objectives: Stimulate economic growth that reduces poverty, create decent jobs and mobilise the entrepreneurial potential of people, in particular the youth and women, in a sustainable manner; support development of private sector and SMEs; support the continental integration process, notably through accelerated infrastructure development, energy, industrialization and investment.

Key areas for cooperation

Private investment, infrastructure and continental integration

39. We will promote continental integration and trade as well as the engagement of the private sector as a key partner in development. This will include strengthening the capacity of stakeholders to develop public-private partnerships. To fast-track the establishment of a Continental Free Trade Area in Africa, the EU offers to draw on its experience of building the Single Market to provide capacity support to this initiative. We will strengthen our cooperation to support initiatives such as Boosting Intra-African Trade and the establishment of the Continental Free Trade Area. We are committed to dialogue on regional and continental economic integration policies. We will work together to foster trade liberalisation and facilitation in a fair manner. The EU will provide support to African countries in the World Trade Organisation (WTO) accession process as well as the implementation of the WTO trade facilitation agreement. This will include the harmonisation of appropriate policies, reducing technical barriers to trade by building capacity to improve, certify and assure the quality and standards of goods.
40. We will continue working on outstanding Economic Partnership Agreements (EPAs) with the aim to foster intra-African trade and Africa's regional integration efforts and the planned Continental Free Trade Area. In this regard, both parties should continue negotiations on EPAs by exploiting all possibilities to reach a satisfactory conclusion of development-oriented and WTO-compatible EPAs that promote African integration, economic transformation and industrialization and ensure the prosperity of nations to the benefit of both continents. It is important that Africa and Europe develop globally competitive industries that can succeed in today's global markets and contribute to sustainable development. EPAs should be structured to ensure that our trade expands and that it supports growth of intra-regional trade in Africa.

41. We will explore modalities to exchange information on the implementation of trade agreements and their implications for Africa's regional integration and industrial development agenda.
42. We will strengthen cooperation in the area of industrial development, through exchange of information and experiences on our respective policy frameworks such as the Europe 2020 Strategy flagship initiatives, an industrial policy for the globalisation era and the Strategy for Accelerated Industrial development (AIDA). Recognising that faster industrialisation is essential for the African countries, we will support the transformation of raw material at the source in order to enable them to reach a middle income status. We shall also work toward prudent and transparent management of respective natural resources in the interest of our populations, in particular in conflict-affected areas in line with principles of good governance. In order to complement the African policies in the above fields, the EU recalls its approach to responsible mineral sourcing and proposes a dialogue on these issues. We will endeavour to cooperate in such fields as geological surveys, mineral resources governance, investment, infrastructure, skills development and waste management.
43. We will engage to develop an open, transparent and predictable investment climate, including through improved legal frameworks, to promote private sector-led trade and responsible investment. We will support small, micro and medium-sized enterprises, which play a strategic role in wealth and job creation in both economies, and foster their competitiveness and internationalisation as well as encourage technology transfer. The EU will put these objectives at the forefront of the EU's support to private sector development and its engagement with the European and African private sectors for development. The EU–Africa Business Forum will remain a privileged platform for exchanges among private companies and with the public sector. Other important stakeholders will be the EU–Africa economic and social actors whose fora should be encouraged and supported.
44. Decisions to invest or develop new policies need to be based on reliable and comparable data. We will enhance cooperation between European and African Statistical Systems in producing quality statistical service.
45. We shall deepen our cooperation in international tax matters to broaden domestic revenue mobilisation and tackle illicit financial flows, through increased cooperation in line with the principles of transparency, exchange of information and fair tax competition.
46. Strategic priorities for cooperation in the fields of energy, transport, water and Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) have been developed

by the Reference Group in Infrastructure through Sector Strategy Papers in coherence with the Programme for Infrastructure Development in Africa (PIDA), the EU Development Policy and other guiding policy frameworks such as the UN Sustainable Energy for All Initiative. Strategic investments in these sectors applying innovative financing approaches will be coupled with support to regulatory reforms. Cross-sectoral coordination will be ensured through the Reference Group on Infrastructure.

47. In the field of transport, we will strive for the reduction of transport costs and boosting of intra-African trade by bringing regional transport corridors to an adequate level of service, which is sustainable, safe and reliable. More attention will be given to the economic, social and environmental dimensions of transport. We will provide sustainable and adequate financial and human resources for the deployment of satellite navigation infrastructure based on European Geostationary Navigation Overlay Service (EGNOS) and establish governance and financing schemes for the capital and operational expenditures of EGNOS in Africa for the countries concerned. Multimodal inter-connections must be the tangible link that unites our two continents and must reflect the privileged relationship between Africa and the EU.

Visit by President of the European Council to Benin. Ceremony of laying the first stone of the Information and Communication Centre of the West African Power Pool (WAPP) in Abomey Calavi, Benin

48. We will progress towards the 2020 targets of the Africa–EU Energy Partnership on Energy access, Energy Security, Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency, with a strong focus on private sector and on interconnections, including between the two continents.
49. Actions in the water sector shall be geared to ensuring sustainable and efficient management of water resources, contributing to growth, peace and security, through institutional strengthening and preparation for investment in multi-purpose water infrastructure. We will ensure better management of water resources for greater access to drinking water and sanitation and strengthen the water-energy-food nexus.
50. In the field of ICT, actions will aim at establishing favorable conditions and enabling environments for ICT in the service of citizens, public authorities and businesses, especially SMEs. This objective will be met through the implementation of a three-pronged ICT for Development Strategy ‘Connecting Africa’ aimed at: a) the harmonisation and alignment of the appropriate aspects of e-communications policies and regulatory frameworks between Africa and the EU, including cyber-security. An important target in this process will be the transition from analogue to digital broadcasting in Africa and the regulation of the resulting Digital Dividend; b) the interconnection of Research and Education Networks through e-infrastructure; and c) the enhancement of ICT capacities for all, particularly in order to improve access to internet and an open and inclusive governance, in line with the Tunis Agenda for the Information Society.

Agriculture, food security and food safety

51. Our work on agriculture, food security and safety will be implemented within the context of the Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme (CAADP) framework. 2014 is the African Year of Agriculture and Food Security and the international year of family farming. This issue features highly in the 2014–2020 EU assistance framework. Not only does agriculture feed people, it also creates sustainable and inclusive growth and jobs. We will endeavour to make our policies converge around a limited number of critical policy indicators to promote a sustainable development of agriculture. We will transform and develop rural areas, forestry and agriculture to create perspectives, jobs and income in particular for rural youth and women. We will address the substantial challenges facing African agriculture in a way that conserves the future productivity of natural resources. Our cooperation in this field will particularly take place within i) the contact group established between the two Commissions and ii) the CAADP partnership.

52. We will develop effective joint approaches to nutrition targets as major components of resilience, by strengthening information systems and analytical tools that support the national policy decision making process (Nutrition Integrated Phase Classification, resilience index, etc.). Regional entities and initiatives, such as the Global Alliance for Resilience Initiative (AGIR), will constitute a privileged framework to promote innovative solutions such as regional emergency food reserves or agriculture risk management.
53. We will promote nutrition sensitive agriculture to contribute to internationally agreed targets to reduce the incidence of stunting. We will increase access to, and year-round availability of, high-nutrient content food, strengthen the capacity of women to provide for the food security, health, and nutrition of their families, as well as improve nutritional knowledge to enhance diet diversity. To monitor progress, explicit nutrition objectives and indicators are incorporated into agricultural project and policy design.
54. We will continue to collaborate on the implementation of the 2009 AU Declaration on Land, using the Framework and Guidelines on Land Policy in Africa (F&G) in line with the Voluntary Guidelines on the responsible Governance of Tenure of land, fisheries and forest (VGGT). Support will be provided to the AU Land Policy Initiative in order to promote land governance frameworks that contribute to improved efficiency, equity and environmental stewardship.
55. We will develop value-adding activities and agribusiness by increasing income opportunities for small holders, especially women, by creating jobs along the agricultural value chains in an inclusive and sustainable manner. We will promote responsible agricultural investment that is crucial for poverty reduction and food security. We therefore encourage the ongoing process preparing principles for responsible agricultural investment in the framework of the Committee on World Food Security. We will support the establishment of new, and expansion of existing, value adding chains for marketing of produce. We will pursue an enhanced cooperation among EU and Africa private sectors and farmers' organisations exploring innovative and inclusive partnerships.
56. We will foster an increase of fair, intra-regional, inter-regional and global trade in agricultural products. We will work for the functioning of transparent and open markets for agricultural products, and build the capacity to serve the respective markets in complying with safety and quality standards, sustainability certification, improving market information systems and value chain governance, and implementing trade facilitation measures to increase cross-border trade. We will strengthen African plant and animal health management systems and compliance with international standards, including by paving the way for the design of an AU–Food safety

Management Coordination Mechanism and a Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed.

57. We will support the implementation of the African Policy Framework for Fisheries and Reform Strategy to unlock the full potential of marine living resources and aquaculture for food security, livelihoods and wealth creation.
58. We will enhance our research on food and nutrition security and sustainable agriculture. We will particularly support the implementation of the medium term operational plans of African regional research and extension organisations and harness the expertise of global agricultural research initiatives to contribute to African research priorities in line with CAADP, the Science Agenda for African Agriculture and the African Agriculture Technology Platform.

Priority area 5: Global and emerging issues

59. Strategic objectives: achieve common positions in global fora and international negotiations and jointly address global challenges.

Key areas for cooperation

Climate change and environment

60. We acknowledge that we share converging views on climate change, environment and natural resource management issues. We will enhance our strategic dialogue on these issues to improve our understanding of the challenges facing Africa, the EU and the global community, and promote joint positions in global negotiations processes.
61. We will jointly undertake efforts to raise pre-2020 greenhouse-gas mitigation ambition and to engage constructively in the negotiation and effective implementation of a new binding global climate change Agreement under the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change and guided by its principles, which will apply to all Parties and must enter into force by 2020 at the latest. In order to ensure that this new agreement applicable to all Parties will be useful, ambitious, fair, balanced, and equitable, we will in particular prepare nationally determined contributions well ahead of the Paris Conference, by the first quarter of 2015, by those Parties ready to do so in accordance with the agreement reached in Conference of Parties19/CMP process.
62. We welcome the statement of African and EU ministers on climate change agreed at the conclusion of their meeting in Brussels on the 1st April 2014.
63. Our dialogue will build on existing processes, such as the Conference of African Heads of States on Climate Change (CAHOSCC) and the African Ministerial Conference on Environment (AMCEN). Joint meetings shall be

organised, as needed, and coordination will be ensured with related sectors such as agriculture and infrastructure.

64. We will ensure the establishment of a coherent framework for the development of Earth Observation activities in Africa so that space strategically contributes to Africa's socio-economic development. Our cooperation will be in line with the priorities of the Africa Space Policy and Strategy and AfriGEOSS, the African segment of the Group on Earth Observation (GEO), in order to deliver services in priority domains for Africa such as food security and health. As part of Africa's contribution to GEO, we will in particular strengthen African capacity to monitor environment and security in Africa using Earth Observation techniques through the implementation of the Global Monitoring for Environment and Security (GMES) and Africa Action Plan and, more specifically, its three priority thematic chapters: marine and coastal areas, water resources and natural resources management.
65. The Monitoring of Environment and Security in Africa (MESA) programme, building on African Monitoring of the Environment for Sustainable Development (AMESD) achievement, will also be an important contribution to these objectives. Recognising the importance of the safety, security and sustainability of outer space activities, we shall continue our dialogue in view of achieving an agreement on an International Code of Conduct for Outer Space Activities. The implementation of other Space policy-related projects will be facilitated by the AU–EU Space Troika.
66. Sustainable land management and the fight against desertification are crucial to support sustainable development. They also contribute to global climate and biodiversity objectives as well as food security. We will continue our engagement in strengthening resilience in Africa, including through programmes such as the Great Green Wall for the Sahara and the Sahel Initiative, the TerrAfrica platform and the EU Global Climate Change Alliance initiative (GCCA), targeting the most vulnerable countries to climate change. Furthermore, we will continue to support the Africa Regional Strategy for Disaster Risk Reduction and to pursue the goals of an African comprehensive disaster resilience framework beyond 2015.
67. We will cooperate to address the global biodiversity crisis and will work on the preservation and the restoration of healthy, resilient ecosystems within and outside protected areas, considering them as a critical natural asset to ensure sustainable livelihood for the people and development of the region. We will also cooperate to integrate biodiversity in national policies, plans and budget. We commit in particular to protect African wildlife by preventing and combatting poaching and trafficking, including through the Wildlife Crisis Window of the EU Biodiversity for life initiative. We will also

stimulate new nature-based business models involving local communities, such as markets for green products and eco-tourism and contribute to implementing the Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS). We will cooperate to implement Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation plus (REDD+) as a central measure to preserve forests and combat climate change. We commit to combating illegal logging (e.g. through the EU Forest Law Enforcement Governance and Trade initiative) as a precondition to sustainable management of forests.

68. Following Rio+20, Africa and the EU will promote the transformation of their economies to become increasingly inclusive and green. Initiatives will support a low-carbon and resource-efficient growth through sustainable consumption and production patterns, green innovation and business development and sound management of energy, chemicals and waste as well as development and extended use of environmentally friendly and energy efficient technologies.

© European Union

Post-2015 Development Agenda

69. Africa and the EU have a strong common interest in working together to secure an ambitious and action-oriented outcome to the post-2015 process, and to ensure that it will be consequently implemented, and in this endeavour will continuously and closely cooperate.
70. To this end we commit to working in partnership during the upcoming negotiations with a view to reaching consensus in 2015. We will consult between groups from our two continents in New York. This will allow for both sides to know their respective priorities, resolve differences of views openly and constructively, identify common interests and discuss developments in global discussions. We will also cooperate to ensure that the implementation of the post-2015 framework and of the 2063 Africa vision, including African development goals, will be complementary, consistent and mutually supportive.

Proliferation of small arms and light weapons and weapons of mass destruction and transfers of conventional arms

71. We will deepen our political dialogue aiming at common positions and proposals in international fora on disarmament and non-proliferation of weapons of mass destruction.
72. We will undertake joint initiatives to strengthen capacities to mitigate against risks linked to chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear (CBRN) materials. We will endeavour to promote the ratification of the Treaty of Pelindaba.
73. Finally, we will undertake joint initiatives to promote and encourage the ratification and implementation of relevant instruments, such as the Anti-personnel Mine Ban Convention, the Convention on Cluster Munitions, the Arms Trade Treaty and of programme such as the UN Programme of Action on Small Arms and Light Weapons (SALW).
74. We remain committed to combat the spread of small arms and light weapons.

Reform of the international governance system

75. We recognize the need to pursue the reform of the main UN bodies with a view to making the overall UN system more effective and transparent and which should be reflective of the substantial changes the international community and UN membership have undergone. In this regard, we will undertake political consultations.

EU–AFRICA DECLARATION ON MIGRATION AND MOBILITY

We, Heads of State and Government of the European Union (EU) and Africa, President of the European Council, the President of the European Commission, the President of the African Union and the Chairperson of the African Union Commission,

ACKNOWLEDGING the benefits that migration and mobility can bring to both our continents, and that a comprehensive approach to migration and mobility are powerful vehicles for boosting sustainable economic, social and environmental development for countries of origin, transit and destination, as well as to migrants themselves;

RECOGNISING our common goal to maximise the development impact of migration and mobility, to improve migration governance and cooperation in countries of origin, transit and destination and to promote the role of migrants as agents of innovation and development;

ACKNOWLEDGING that migration and mobility between and within our continents present both opportunities and challenges;

STRESSING the importance of addressing the root causes of irregular migration between Africa and Europe and bearing in mind the importance of finding alternatives to this phenomenon including by providing employment opportunities for the youth at regional level;

ACKNOWLEDGING that further efforts should be made to better organise legal migration and to foster well-managed mobility as well as to encourage policies that facilitate labour migration, including at the regional level;

DEEPLY CONCERNED by the serious social and human impact of irregular migration and the loss of life caused by it, and more than ever committed to undertake action to avoid such tragedies in future by effectively tackling irregular migration and adopting a comprehensive approach to migration management, within the context of strict observance of human rights and human dignity;

EXPRESSING GREAT CONCERN that trafficking of human beings as a modern day form of slavery constitutes a serious crime and an infringement of the fundamental human rights of the victims;

UNDERSCORING the importance of prosecuting smugglers and traffickers and dismantling their criminal networks as they present a serious threat to the lives of migrants;

RECOGNISING that Diasporas create strong human ties between our continents and that they contribute significantly to the development of countries of origin and destination;

REITERATING our common commitment to fight all forms of discrimination, racism and xenophobia, and all acts of intolerance on both continents, and to ensure that the human rights of migrants, including those of the diaspora and victims of trafficking, are fully respected in both continents;

STRESSING that fully enforcing the international legal instruments on international protection is an urgent need that should be promoted and placed at the centre of the Africa–EU cooperation;

RECALLING the importance of maintaining the link between migration and mobility policies and other policy areas, especially employment and higher education, within the broader framework of the Africa–EU Partnership;

COMMITTING to further dialogue and deepening of our cooperation in the field of migration and mobility within the framework of the Joint Africa–EU Strategy, through a global and concerted approach to maximise their development impact on both Africa and the EU;

We express our strong and unambiguous political will to address all the challenges related to inter and intra-continental migration and mobility and to build on their opportunities.

We commit to ensuring that the importance of well-managed migration and mobility as drivers of inclusive growth and sustainable development will be adequately reflected in the post-2015 development agenda.

We commit to undertaking concrete actions to respond to challenges of migration and mobility at the appropriate level in a spirit of partnership, shared responsibility and cooperation.

To this end, we agree on an Action Plan for 2014–2017 focusing on the following key areas:

- We undertake to upscale our efforts in combating trafficking in human beings, notably by strengthening partnership and cooperation on prevention, protection and prosecution as well as fighting against those taking advantage of all forms of exploitation, both in Europe and in Africa;
- We commit to fight irregular migration, by promoting comprehensive and efficient cooperation to avoid the dramatic consequences of irregular migration and to safeguard the lives of migrants, addressing all its relevant aspects, including prevention, strengthened migration and

border management, the fight against smuggling of migrants, return and readmission (including voluntary return) as well as addressing the root causes of irregular migration;

- We commit to strengthen the nexus between migration and development, including by stepping up efforts to significantly reduce the costs of remittances, consolidate the African Institute for Remittances and strengthen policy frameworks for enhancing Diaspora engagement;
- We agree to advance legal migration and mobility, by better organising legal migration and fostering well-managed mobility between and within the continents;
- We agree to strengthen international protection, including through the implementation of international and regional instruments for the protection of refugees, asylum seekers and internally displaced persons.

We recall that the respect of the fundamental human rights of migrants, irrespective of their legal status, constitutes a cross-cutting issue of our cooperation.

EU-Africa Summit Sommet UE-Afrique

Bruxelles **2014** Brussels

LIST OF PARTICIPANTS

CO-PRESIDENCY

EUROPEAN COUNCIL

Herman Van Rompuy,
President

EUROPEAN COMMISSION

José Manuel Barroso,
President

AFRICAN UNION

Mohamed Ould Abdel Aziz,
President

AFRICAN UNION COMMISSION

Nkosazana Clarice Dlamini Zuma,
Chairperson

ALGERIA
(People's Democratic
Republic of Algeria)

Youcef Yousfi,
Prime Minister

ANGOLA
(Republic of Angola)

Manuel Domingos Vicente,
Vice-President

AUSTRIA

Werner Faymann,
Federal Chancellor

BELGIUM

Elio Di Rupo,
Prime Minister

BENIN
(Republic of Benin)

Thomas Boni Yayi,
President

BOTSWANA
(Republic of Botswana)

Phandu Tombola Chaka Skelemani,
Minister for Foreign Affairs

BULGARIA

Rosen Assenov Plevneliev,
President

BURKINA FASO

Blaise Compaoré,
President

BURUNDI

(Republic of Burundi)

Pierre Nkurunziza,
President

CABO VERDE

(Republic of Cabo Verde)

Jorge Carlos De Almeida Fonseca,
President

CAMEROON

(Republic of Cameroon)

Paul Biya,
President

CHAD

(Republic of Chad)

Idriss Déby Itno,
President

COMOROS

(Union of the Comoros)

Ikililou Dhoinine,
President

CONGO

(Republic of the Congo)

Denis Sassou Nguesso,
President

CÔTE D'IVOIRE

(Republic of Côte d'Ivoire)

Daniel Kablan Duncan,
Prime Minister

CROATIA

Zoran Milanović,
Prime Minister

CYPRUS

Nicos Anastasiades,
President of the Republic

CZECH REPUBLIC

Bohuslav Sobotka,
Prime Minister

DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC OF THE CONGO

Raymond Tshibanda
N'tunga Mulongoa,
Minister for Foreign Affairs

DENMARK

Helle Thorning-Schmidt,
Prime Minister

DJIBOUTI

(Republic of Djibouti)

Ismail Omar Guelleh,
President

EGYPT

(Arab Republic of Egypt)

Nabil Fahmy,
Minister for Foreign Affairs

ÉIRE/IRELAND

Enda Kenny,
The Taoiseach

EQUATORIAL GUINEA

(Republic of Equatorial Guinea)

Teodoro Obiang Nguema Mbasogo,
President

ERITREA

(State of Eritrea)

Osman Saleh Mohammed,
Minister for Foreign Affairs

ESTONIA

Taavi Rõivas,
Prime Minister

ETHIOPIA

(Federal Democratic
Republic of Ethiopia)

Hailemariam Desalegn,
Prime Minister

FINLAND

Jyrki Katainen,
Prime Minister

FRANCE

François Hollande,
President of the Republic

GABON

(Gabonese Republic)

Ali Bongo Ondimba,
President

THE GAMBIA

(Republic of the Gambia)

Momodou Sabally,
Secretary general and
Minister for Presidential Affairs

GERMANY

Angela Merkel,
Federal Chancellor

GHANA

(Republic of Ghana)

John Dramani Mahama,
President

GREECE

Evangelos Venizelos,
Minister for Foreign Affairs

GUINEA

(Republic of Guinea)

Alpha Condé,
President

HUNGARY

János Martonyi,
Ministry for Foreign Affairs

ITALY

Matteo Renzi,
Prime Minister

KENYA

(Republic of Kenya)

Uhuru Kenyatta,
President

LATVIA

Laimdota Straujuma,
Prime Minister

LESOTHO

(Kingdom of Lesotho)

Motsoahae Thomas Thabane,
Prime Minister

LIBERIA

(Republic of Liberia)

Ellen Johnson Sirleaf,
President

LIBYA

(State of Libya)

Represented
at ambassadorial level

LITHUANIA

Algirdas Butkevičius,
Prime Minister

LUXEMBOURG

Jean Asselborn,
Minister for Foreign Affairs

MADAGASCAR

(Republic of Madagascar)

Hery Rajaonarimampianina,
President

MALAWI

(Republic of Malawi)

Ephraim Mganda Chume,
Minister for Foreign Affairs

MALI

(Republic of Mali)

Ibrahim Boubacar Keïta,
President

MALTA

Joseph Muscat,
Prime Minister

MAURITANIA

(Islamic Republic of Mauritania)

Mohamed Ould Abdel Aziz,
President

MAURITIUS

(Republic of Mauritius)

Navinchandra Ramgoolam,
Prime Minister

MOROCCO

(Kingdom of Morocco)

Salaheddine Mezouar,
Minister for Foreign Affairs

MOZAMBIQUE

(Republic of Mozambique)

Armando Emilio Guebuza,
President

NAMIBIA

(Republic of Namibia)

Hifikepunye Pohamba,
President

NETHERLANDS

Mark Rutte,
Prime Minister

NIGER

(Republic of Niger)

Mahmadou Issoufou,
President

NIGERIA

(Federal Republic of Nigeria)

Goodluck Ebele Jonathan,
President

POLAND

Donald Tusk,
Prime Minister

PORTUGAL

Pedro Passos Coelho,
Prime Minister

ROMANIA

Traian Băsescu,
President

RWANDA
(Republic of Rwanda)

Paul Kagamé,
President

SÃO TOMÉ AND PRÍNCIPE
(Democratic Republic of São Tomé
and Príncipe)

Manuel Pinto da Costa,
President

SENEGAL
(Republic of Senegal)

Macky Sall,
President

SEYCHELLES
(Republic of Seychelles)

Jean Paul Adam,
Minister for Foreign Affairs

SIERRA LEONE
(Republic of Sierra Leone)

Ernest Bai Koroma,
President

SLOVAKIA

Miroslav Lajčák,
Deputy Prime Minister

SLOVENIA

Borut Pahor,
President

SOMALIA
(Federal Republic of Somalia)

Hassan Sheikh Mohamud,
President

SOUTH AFRICA
(Republic of South Africa)

Maite Emily Nkoana-Mashabane,
Minister of International Relations
and Cooperation

SOUTH SUDAN
(Republic of South Sudan)

Awan Andrew Guol Riak,
Minister in the Office
of the President

SPAIN

Mariano Rajoy Brey,
Prime Minister

SUDAN
(Republic of the Sudan)

Ali Ahmed Karti,
Minister for Foreign Affairs

SWAZILAND
(Kingdom of Swaziland)

Mswati III,
King

SWEDEN

Carl Bildt,
Minister for Foreign Affairs

TANZANIA
(United Republic of Tanzania)

Jakaya Kikwete,
President

TOGO
(Togolese Republic)

Komlan Edo Robert Dussey,
Minister for Foreign Affairs
and Cooperation

TUNISIA
(Tunisian Republic)

Moncef Marzouki,
President

UGANDA
(Republic of Uganda)

Yoweri Kaguta Museveni,
President

UNITED KINGDOM

William Hague,
Secretary of State for Foreign
and Commonwealth Affairs

ZAMBIA (Republic of Zambia)

Michael Chilufya Sata,
President

SPECIAL GUESTS

UNITED NATIONS

Ban Ki-Moon,
Secretary General

AFRICAN DEVELOPMENT BANK

Donald Kaberuka,
President

EUROPEAN INVESTMENT BANK

Pim Van Ballekom,
Vice President

PAN AFRICAN PARLIAMENT

Bethel Nnaemeka Amadi,
President

EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT

Miguel Angel Martínez
Martínez,
Vice President

EUROPEAN EXTERNAL ACTION SERVICE

Catherine Ashton
High Representative
of the Union for Foreign
Affairs and Security
Policy

LIST OF EU–AFRICA SUMMITS

Cairo	April 2000
Lisbon	December 2007
Tripoli	November 2010
Brussels	April 2014

EU-Africa Summit
Sommet UE-Afrique
Bruxelles 2014 Brussels

02-03.04.2014

EU-Africa Summit
Sommet UE-Afrique
Bruxelles 2014 Brussels

Rue de la Loi/Wetstraat 175
1048 Bruxelles/Brussel
BELGIQUE/BELGIË
Tel. +32 (0)2 281 61 11
www.consilium.europa.eu

Publications Office

QC-02-14-974-EN-N

ISBN 978-92-824-4656-0
doi:10.2860/55618